
Preparing for Video-lecturing: A Toolkit

Project Learn.Inc

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Purpose of the document

This toolkit is created within the frame of Project 2021-1-RO01-KA220-HED-000031136 Learn.Inc. It is designed to provide aid, guidelines and common standards for partner teams to prepare video lecture courses not only for the purposes of the current initiative, but as free and useful tool in their further endeavors in the field of open and digital learning.

Authors

It was prepared by an international team comprising: Vassiliki Takouli (Hellenic Open University), Fotini Tatsi (Hellenic Open University), Katerina Galanou (Hellenic Open University), Nikolay Yanev (Sofia University), Snezhina Gabova (Research & Training Point Foundation).

The document covers several topics: 1) General methodology for the design and development of a video-lecture course, 2) Guidelines and instructions for designing educational content, 3) Instructions for preparing assessment tools and 4) Instructions for the implementation of project result 3 within the frame of Learn.Inc.

General methodology for the design and development of a video-lectured course (VLC)

Vassiliki Takouli, Fotini Tatsi, Katerina Galanou

Following one of the classical methodological approaches, the preparation for a VLC course could be streamlined along the following steps:

1. Analysis

During the analysis phase the training challenge that will be addressed through the VLC is analyzed in order to specify the purpose of training, the knowledge domain, the main learning goals, the basic learning objectives, the learners' profile and the timeframe of the training process. It is equally important to define the learners' background knowledge and to set any necessary limitations and knowledge prerequisites.

EXAMPLE

The "Strategic planning: Making real what matters for modern ecosystems" course will last 4 weeks. Each week, of 10 hours of study in total, will contain 3 modules (chapters / sections) (e.g. a module is equivalent to a strategic thinking (ST) competence, or a strategic decision-making competence or a business transformation competence).

Every module described above consists of 4 units (learning activities – subchapters / subsections). In each unit (learning activity) an educational strategy should be applied in order to deliver any combination of core learning medium (video), additional educational material (e.g. e-books, additional readings, etc), collaborative formats (e.g. forum) and assessment methods (self-evaluation exercises, quizzes) in order learners to fulfill specific learning outcomes.

RECOMMENDED ACTION

Please fill in the templates labeled

→ TA1: Course Description

2. Design Phase

The design phase is the most essential and demanding one in the particular DC (Distant Course) development methodology. The purpose of this phase is to define and describe the detailed learning objectives for each module; the units (learning activities) in which each module is divided; the educational strategy that will be applied in each unit and the learning outcomes of each unit. In this phase, it is equally important to define the students' assessment method. Consequently, the learning objects should be designed according to the learning outcomes, as described above.

It should be noted that units (learning activities) demonstrate the way that knowledge (learning objects, additional educational material, quizzes, wikis, projects etc.) should be provided to the learners according to the educational strategy adopted.

RECOMMENDED ACTION

Please fill in the templates labeled

- TB1: Course Module Description / Schedule
- TB2: Course Unit (Learning Activity) Description
- TB3: Learning Object/Medium Description
- TB3a: Assessment Object Design and Production

3. Development Phase

The development phase includes the production of the educational material (content) which is based on the design realized in the previous phase.

The learning objects (core, additional supportive material, collaboration and assessment learning objects) are developed as conceived in the previous phase according to their technical type with respect to their learning resource type and subsequently uploaded to the DC platform. It is recommended to use the educational material guidelines provided, since there are providing instructions on "what to do" and "what to avoid" during the development process. These guidelines are provided for both the pedagogical and technical aspect of an educational material.

During the development phase, authors could collaborate with multimedia developers, video experts (technical staff), who could contribute in creating or editing qualitative educational videos and additional digital educational material as described in the design phase.

Simultaneously, the technical team sets the DC Platform, integrates the educational material into the platform (according to the course module, learning activities templates) and creates the platform manuals.

4. Implementation Phase

During this phase, the educational process is implemented as designed and developed in the previous phases and the learning effectiveness is evaluated. The primary goal of this phase is the dissemination and publication of the course. The course can be promoted and disseminated via the social networks, advertising, communities and email databases, newsletters and relevant websites of culture. Before delivering the actual course, a pilot course should run in order to test and evaluate it, and the functionality of the platform for potential improvements. The participants in the pilot course could be a small number of learners and the experienced scientific staff (trainers). After the completion of the pilot course, improvements could be made to both the platform and the course, according to the comments and reviews by both parties – trainers and trainees.

Subsequently, the education process in a Short Learning Programme (SLP) course will be realized in a predefined time period since tutors and technical staff must support, operate, monitor and audit the education process through the platform.

5. Evaluation Phase

The evaluation of the proposed methodology shall be conducted in two directions. Formative evaluations should take place in every phase while the final evaluation takes place at the end of all phases, in order to uncover improvement issues. Therefore, the evaluation consists of formative and summative assessment, which includes:

- (A) **Formative Assessment:** The formative evaluation is conducted in each stage of the process and includes information collection (check sheets, focus groups results, interviews, questionnaires etc.) in order to identify problems. During the procedure, revisions must be done whenever evaluation considers it necessary. The purpose of the formative evaluation is (a) to estimate the correct implementation of every step of the development process and (b) to verify the scientific quality of the course.
- (B) **Summative Assessment:** The final assessment measures the effectiveness of the educational process; providing feedback from users and team members using interviews, system logs (providing information of platform usage, rates of attendance in every activity etc.), questionnaires etc.

Appendix: Course and module description tables

Table 1 – TA1: Course Description (Analysis Phase)

TA1: Course Description		
1	Course (DC) title	
2	Course description	<i>This course addresses the needs of (1)</i>
3	Knowledge domain	<i>Knowledge domains of the course are</i> •
4	Educational problem	<i>The particular course addresses....</i>
5	Course addressed to	<i>This course addresses the basic</i>
6	Course type	Part time
7	Learning goals	<i>Main learning goals</i> •
8	Basic learning objectives	<i>Basic learning objectives (4 up to 10)</i> • <i>competitive business strategies</i>
9	Course length	xxx weeks
10	Learners' profile	<i>The learners are....</i>
11	Learners' background knowledge	<i>Learners must</i>
12	Participation prerequisites
13	Special needs from the educational environment

Table 2 – TB1: Course Module Description (Design Phase)

TB1: Course Module Description		
1	Course Module code	...
2	Course Module title
3	Course Module description	<i>Description of the module (up to 100 words)</i>
4	Knowledge domain	→
5	Learning objectives	<i>Learning objectives (4 up to 10) for the specific module</i>

Table 3 – TB2: Course Unit Description (Design Phase)

(*) A unit (learning activity) should be approximately 0,5–1 hours of study

TB2: Course Unit (Learning Activity) Description		
1	Unit code	<i>(as defined in Table 2 (TB1))</i>
2	Unit title	<i>(as specified in Table 2 (TB1))</i>
3	Unit description	<i>Description of the Unit (learning activity) (up to 100 words)</i>
4	Educational strategy	<i>Description of the educational strategy (e.g. presentation, role playing, case study) will be adopted for the specific unit (learning activity)</i>
5	Learning outcomes (LOut)	<i>Record the Learning Outcomes for the specific unit (use Table's TB1 codes)</i>
6	Unit core (self-produced) material (Learning object (LO)) (code and title)	<i>List of Learning objects (videos, presentations, etc.) included in the specific unit (codes should be consistent and should reflect the corresponding unit) (for each core material specified here please fill in a Table TB3)</i>

7	Unit additional (Open.Education.Resources.) material (code and title)	List of additional material (e-books, additional readings, etc) included in the specific unit (codes should be consistent and should reflect the corresponding unit) (for each additional material specified here please fill in a Table TB3)
8	Collaboration objects (code and title)	List of Collaboration objects (e.g. forum) included in the specific unit (codes should be consistent and should reflect the corresponding unit) (for each collaboration material specified here please fill in a Table TB3)
9	Assessment methods (projects, self-evaluation exercises, etc.) (code and title)	Detailed description of the learners' assessment for the specific unit (codes should be consistent and should reflect the corresponding unit) (for each assessment object specified here please fill in a Table TB3a)
10	Unit schedule	Description of the educational path for the defined unit
11	Key words	Key words (3 to 10)

Table 4 – TB3: Learning Object (Design Phase)

TB3: Learning Object		
1	Learning object code	(as defined in Table 3 (TB2))
2	Learning object title	(as defined in Table 3 (TB2))
3	Learning object description	Description of the Learning object (up to 100 words) *
4	Language	English
5	Learning recourse type (IEEE LOM)	Definition of the learning resource type (theory, simulation, experiment, etc.) for the specific learning object (select one from the list in Table 5)

6	Technical type (IEEE LOM)	<i>Definition of the technical type (document, video, wiki etc.) for the specific learning object</i>
7	Workload (Estimated study time) (min)	<i>The estimated study time needed for an average learner in minutes:</i>
8	Key words	<i>Key words (3 to 10)</i>
9	Learning outcomes (LOut)	<i>Record the Learning Outcomes for the specific learning object (should be a subset of the learning outcomes defined in the corresponded unit (learning activity)). In case you define more learning outcomes than those defined in the relative unit (learning activity) please update appropriately the relative unit learning outcomes field.</i>

TB3a: Learning Object (Assessment Object)

1	Learning object code	<i>(as defined in Table 3 (TB2))</i>	
2	Learning object title	<i>Title of Learning object(as defined in Table 3 (TB2))</i>	
3	Language		
4	Learning recourse type (IEEE LOM)	<i>Definition of the learning recourse type (theory, simulation, experiment, etc.) for the specific learning object (select from the list in Table 8)</i>	
5	Technical type (IEEE LOM)	<i>Text</i>	<i>Document</i>
6	Workload (Estimated study time) (min)	<i>The estimated study time needed for an average learner in minutes</i>	
7	Write down the assessment methods (quiz)	<i>Use the template below as many times as needed and modify accordingly to specific question type (1 template for each question).</i>	

Table 7 – TB3a: Assessment Object Design and Production (Design Phase)

Question template	
No.	1.
Question (stem)	
Possible answers	
Correct answer	
Response to correct answer	Very good, you can proceed to the next question
Response to wrong answer(s)	It's false, you can repeat the effort
Times the question can be taken	The number is: 1
Is the question part of a test?	

During the design of educational material and even before its development, authors should have completed the above Template for each of the learning objects, according to the content of their object.

Instructions for completing the TB3

1) You should fill in one TB3 table for each learning (core material), additional and collaboration object and one TB3a table for each self-assessment object defined in the first part of the design phase.

2) You should fill in all fields provided but you should pay attention to the field 7 where you should define approximately the estimated study time (workload) in minutes.

The workload for a textual learning object depends on the content. In the case of a journal article, it is approximately 3–4 pages an hour; if it is a book chapter then 5 pages per hour are more appropriate. In case the content is even easier, increase pages per hour accordingly.

→ A safe way to estimate a video learning object workload is to double its duration. For example, if the video lasts 4 minutes, the study/comprehension time for the video is 8 minutes approximately.

→ The workload of a hypertext is the sum of the text itself plus the workload of each object it links to.

→ For each self-assessment object, the workload estimation is the accumulation / sum of each individual question's workload this object consists of. Workload for questions of types like "multiple choice" or "fill in the blanks" or "matching" is more or less 5 min (each) and questions of type "yes/no (or true/false)" is more or less 3 min (each).

Please notice that content information prior to the production phase is considered crucial in order to avoid possible unnecessary process backtracking.

Important notifications:

→ Please notice that the total of STUDY EFFORT = time of work study + comprehension + the time needed for the assessment (after the educational material the trainee should do quizzes, multiple choice questions, self –evaluation exercises etc).

→ The content of the self-assessment objects should also be approved by the scientific reviewers.

Guidelines & Instructions for Designing Educational Content

Nikolay Yanev, Vassiliki Takouli, Snezhina Gabova

Technical instructions for developing video lectures/courses

Another option is to develop educational material and provide it to learners as a self – running presentation or a video.

Video – What is it?

Video is an electronic medium for the recording, processing, storing, copying, playback, broadcasting, and display of moving visual media. A video can be processed, inserting comments or subtitles, presentations, sounds etc. Digital video is an electronic representation of moving visual images (video) in the form of encoded digital data (digital media used for the recording, processing and storing processes).

The most common video types, related to educational content, include interviews, conversations, lectures, directed scenarios and screencasts.

Interview

An interview is a conversation including questions and answers. A person (the interviewer) asks predefined questions, while the invited persons (interviewees) respond (usually within predetermined time), with participants talk in turns.

Interviews usually involve a transfer of information from the interviewee to the interviewer (and therefore to the audience), which is usually the primary purpose of the interview.

Slides can also be inserted (in a presentation form) or images, while the interviewee speaks, in order to make the response more conceivable.

Conversation

A conversation is an interactive communication between two or more people on a specific subject. In conversations, we can also add slides (in presentation form) or images, in order to make the speaker more understandable.

Lecture

A lecture is an oral presentation with the purpose to present information, or teach people or students a particular subject, usually using slides in presentation form or images.

Directed scenario

This type of video usually refers to a presentation of a specific object. For example, it presents an exhibit (a painting, a sculpture, etc.) in a museum, a sightseeing, an experiment, etc. Usually it includes also audio narrations for the pictures presented. Actors or speakers can be included (optionally) so as to make the presentation more vivid.

Screencast

A screencast (also known as a video screen capture) is a digital recording of the computer screen output, containing often also audio narration. The term screencast is compared to the related term screenshot; whereas screenshot generates a single picture of a computer screen, a screencast is essentially a movie of the changes over time that a user sees on a computer screen, enhanced with audio narration.

Technical tips

While recording the video we should pay attention to some technical details.

The video lecture has visual and audio components.

VIDEO tips

- The camera you use should be able to produce high-resolution, sharp picture
- The shooting should preferably be done using two identical cameras at the same time; one for a close-up shot and one for a medium shot (from waist up). Make sure to arrange the same settings to both cameras (ISO, White Balance, fps, aperture, shutter speed).
- Keep your videos up to 7 minutes maximum (without cuts) in total, in order to keep the audience interested. If it is not possible to film for 7 minutes straight, split the video in two parts.
- The preferable frame rate is 25fps.
- Avoid camera movements; the use of tripods and other mechanical stabilization is strongly encouraged.
- Capture should focus on the presenters and keep the camera on eye-level.
- Do not change the video settings or lighting during the recording.
- Check the lighting conditions and take care to use properly adjusted artificial light sources (avoid "burned" or dark picture)
- Check the focus before and during the recording. Depending on the camera settings and the light conditions it might need corrections.

- During the recording of the lecture the cameras should focus on the lecturer.

AUDIO tips

Sound is a crucial and often underestimated element in the video. Therefore:

- Opt for high-end, high-quality microphones
- It is preferable to record sounds using lavalier microphones, which are connected with the camera.
- Avoid echoing. Before you start recording, check the acoustics of the place.
- It is necessary to clap (hands or with a clapper) in the center of the frame after you make sure that the camera and the sound are rolling. Before clapping, the camera operator or the director should say clearly the title of the interview and the clip (for example "Management 2.1, take 1").

EDITING tips

- The slides of the presentation should not appear in the frame of the video; they will be added later during video editing.
- The editing phase is suitable for sound enhancement

Tips For the Presenters

- Presenters should use simple language, without complex terms. If they have to use a complex term, they should explain it briefly.
- Presenters should avoid wearing: white, black, brands.
- When there is only one presenter, he/she should focus their look into the camera.
- Presenters should not speak quickly and not hold anything in their hands.
- The selection of lecturers should also take into account their quality as narrators – some voices have stronger effect on the listener, some speakers are better in articulating clear and distinctive messages. Not everyone is fit for the camera and film
- Presenters should not speak too close or too far from the microphone. Make sure that each speaker's voice sounds clearly.
- They should have prepared their speeches and (if technically possible) -read them through autocue (there are online applications, e.g. <http://www.freeteleprompter.org>). The autocue should be placed on top of the camera or at eye-level. All questions and answers should be written down and rehearsed before the shooting.
- The presenter may choose if he/she wants to speak standing up or seated down.

- In case we want to add graphics on the side of the frame, the presenter should stand/ sit on the right half of the frame.
- The make-up should be plain and discreet. Likewise, for the hair.

Background –, Scene and Surroundings

- The background should be empty and of a bright color for graphics in white color, or of a dark color in case of graphics in black color. Avoid backgrounds with designs / patterns or objects.
- There should be lots of light making sure that no intense shadows are created on the presenter or on the background. The face should look clear and bright.
- Avoid burning the picture with extreme light as well as the strong shadows
- Avoid direct light in the eyes, which can distract the lecturer.
- Avoid or eliminate external sounds. Please record in isolated places or in a studio. However, if you choose to shoot at an exterior space, make sure that it is not too noisy and no people interfere in the frame. An exterior shooting should be done only in case a professional is in charge.

Footage

- The footage of the shooting should be sent accompanied by the text of the speech and the “ppt” presentation or any other material that needs to be shown (video/ image etc.) stating when it should be displayed.

Examples

Please visit the following videos to get some ideas:

- ❖ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uSqKMmFRGuA&index=17&list=PL_ovOkIxA5utev8Sery_4rMbV2uGho6fc
- ❖ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mjuOFw9VjIw&index=19&list=PL_ovOkIxA5utev8Sery_4rMbV2uGho6fc
- ❖ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ymNMABkTuRY&index=34&list=PL_ovOkIxA5utdZP8LX5hbw6BMczDSsriC

Miscellaneous

Educational material should be self-guided and enhance student interaction with it. Explanatory examples and encouraging comments are recommended. At the beginning of each section, the learning goals and the expected learning outcomes should be defined, as well as a synopsis of the lecture at the end.

Technical instructions for developing online distance learning presentations

The presentation designed as a useful resource for a distance (online) learning should contain some of the following elements (elements marked with an # are considered mandatory):

- 1) Elements at the beginning of the presentation
 - a) Title slide #
 - b) b. Aim / objectives #
 - c) c. Learning outcomes #
 - d) d. Keywords #
 - e) e. Table of contents
- 2) Elements in the body of the presentation
 - a) a. Sections / sub sections #
 - b) b. Tables / Graphs / Figures
- 3) Elements at the end of the presentation
 - a) Synopsis
 - b) List of references
 - c) Further reading
 - d) Presenters' bio/contact information
 - e) Credits #

In the following paragraphs, each of these elements is briefly explained. It is assumed that each presentation is accompanied by a narration.

Title slide (1 slide)

Shows the title of the presentation, together with contextual information (e.g. module / unit it belongs to). The name(s) of the presenter(s) could also appear here.

Aim / objectives (1 slide)

The aim provides a brief explanation of the general contribution of the presentation. The objectives outline the aim in more concrete terms. A brief introduction to the topic of the presentation could be provided here, too.

Learning outcomes (1 slide)

They describe the knowledge / skills / competences (attitudes) that the student will develop after the presentation. They should be based on Bloom's taxonomy and specialize some of the learning outcomes of the module. A sample introductory phrase is "After examining this resource, you will be able to: ..." (followed by a list of outcomes). The list should contain about 5 learning outcomes (approximately).

Table of contents (1 slide)

Provides an overview of the presentation contents. If the presentation contains sections and sub-section, they should be mentioned here, together with the main slide titles of each. This is an alternative location for a brief introduction to the topic of the presentation.

Keywords (1slide)

A set of keywords/glossary that introduces the main terms used in the document, together with a brief explanation. The list should not contain more than 10 terms; 6 is a good number.

Sections / subsections

These parts create the core/the body of the presentation. In general, the main content of the presentation should be structured in a way that allows it to be viewed in non-sequential (i.e. the student can jump to any subsection) and modular (i.e. the student can stop at the end of a section and continue later) ways. The entire presentation and each section could be preceded by an introduction.

Tables, figures and graphs

It is better to place them next to the text, or in a stand-alone slide (without text). Avoid placing text in random positions around graphical elements. Any graphical materials should be large enough to be discernible and legible.

Synopsis (1 slide)

The synopsis is placed at the end of the presentation and summarizes its contents and the learner's achievements from watching it.

List of references (1 slide) Contains the list of resources used in the presentation. Use either APA or IEEE style. Even if references are also placed in the slides that make up the body of the presentation, they should be summarized at the end as well.

Further reading (1 slide)

Provides open educational resources (OERs) for further reading. For each resource, provide its reference (using APA or IEEE style) and a brief summary (no more than 5 lines).

Presenters' bio (1 slide per presenter)

Ideally, the presenters should present themselves. This can be done either in the beginning (i.e. after the title slide) or at the end of the presentation. A short textual bio with a photo should be shown, while each presenter speaks briefly

about him/herself in first person (i.e. Hello, I am ... and, in this presentation, we shall ... - tenses should be adapted accordingly).

Credits (1 slide)

Thanks, the student for watching the presentation. Shows the names of the contributors to the presentation (i.e. author(s), narrator(s), visual effects creator(s), musical score author(s) etc.) and contact details if further communication from the student is necessary. Also shows the licensing mode and takes into account the EU publication requirements.

Technical instructions for developing online distance learning textual material

In order to provide textual educational material to learners, a written document could be provided. For a document to be useful as an online distance learning resource, it should contain some of the following elements (elements marked with an # are considered mandatory):

- 1) Elements at the start of the document
 - a) Aim / objectives #
 - b) Learning outcomes #
 - c) Keywords #
 - d) Introduction
 - e) Pre-requisite knowledge
 - f) Table of contents / figures / tables
- 2) Elements in the body of the document
 - a) Sections / sub sections #
 - b) Tables
 - c) Figures
 - d) Examples
 - e) Case studies
- 3) Elements at the end of the document
 - a) Synopsis
 - b) List of references
 - c) Glossary
 - d) Further reading

The following paragraphs provide short instructions to each of these structural documents.

Aim / objectives

The aim section provides a brief explanation of the general contribution of the document. The objectives outline the aim using more concrete terms. This element should not exceed 5 lines of text.

Learning outcomes

They describe the knowledge / skills / competences (attitudes) that the student will develop after studying the document. They should be based on Bloom's

taxonomy and should focus on some of the learning outcomes of the module. Template introductory phrases might be: "After studying this resource, you will be able to..." (followed by a list of outcomes). The list should not contain more than 10 outcomes; 5 is a good number.

Keywords

A set of keywords describes the most important terms/notions used in the document. Note that for each of these terms, an explanation should be provided in the text and they could be summarized in the glossary. The first appearance of a term should be easily identifiable (i.e. using boldface). The list should not contain more than 10 terms; 6 is a good number.

Introduction

Introduces the reader to the contents. Places the resource in context and associates it with any previously covered material (if applicable). This part also summarizes the resource contents. The introduction should be used only for medium-sized and long documents (i.e. more than 4 pages). It should not exceed 10% of the total length of the document.

Prerequisite knowledge

In this part you should list the minimum knowledge and skills needed in order to make the best use of the resource. This part might not be useful for short or medium-sized documents. It could be part of the introduction. The description should not exceed 10 lines of text.

Table of contents / figures / tables (TOC)

The TOC provides an overview of the content and allows direct access to parts of the document. It should be used in long documents only (i.e. more than 12 pages).

Sections / subsections

The sections structure the body of the document. It is a text, laid in paragraphs. Avoid using more than 3 levels. For clarity they could be numbered.

Tables, figures and graphs

Tables and graphs are used to illustrate a deliver messages, ideas, processes, facts etc. Figures usually clarify or the text. It is preferable to place such visual elements within the text, or at the marginal space (if enough space is provided); avoiding wrapping the text around them.

In most cases it is better to place them within a frame.

The size and the resolutions should allow legibility. Numbers and captions facilitate referencing and navigation and are a must. When referring to such

illustrations the author should write “in figure 1/see figure 1”, and avoid expressions like “in the following figure”.

In case the document will be printed, one should be careful with the use of colors (and the references made to them).

Examples and case studies

They are used to contextualize or personalize a part of the document based on real and imaginary situations. These elements should be placed within a frame. Titles and numbers are essential. When referenced from the text, one should write “in example 1/case 1”, never write “in the following example/case”.

Synopsis

The synopsis belongs to the end of the document and summarizes its contents and the learner’s achievements. It should be used only for medium-sized and long documents (i.e. more than 4 pages). Its volume should not exceed 5% of the total length of the document.

List of references

This part contains the list of resources referenced to in the text. The list should either be numbered or placed in alphabetical order. Use either APA or IEEE style. Make sure that each item in the list is referenced at least once in the text.

Glossary

The glossary lists the important terms used (or introduced) in the text in alphabetical order, with a brief explanation.

Further reading

This part of the textual material provides selected resources (OERs) for further reading. For each resource, provide its reference (using APA or IEEE style) and a brief summary (no more than 5 lines).

Assessment methods

Assessment method – What is it?

In the academic context, learning materials are designed based on predetermined expectations and students are evaluated according to the extent they master these expectations. In order to evaluate the degree of mastery of these expectations in learning we usually use assessment methods.

One of the most common assessment objects used is the quiz in which the trainees (as individuals or in teams) attempt to answer questions correctly. It is a "game" to test their knowledge about a certain subject, in order to refine programs and improve their learning.

Quizzes

Quizzes are usually scored in points and many of them are designed to determine the student's success in the learning process. This can be made by grading and weighing each question's correct answer (sometimes you can also add negative grading in wrong answers).

Quizzes consisting of a number of questions can be categorized in:

- Open-ended questions which are hard to assess automatically, but can be used to initiate some individual activity (e.g. read this article and comment...) or even better some group activity (e.g. after reading this article, join the forum discussion about the "XYZ" topic and present your opinion).
- Closed-ended questions which are ideal for an automated assessment. The most common types of this kind of questions are: Multiple Choice Questions (MCQ), fill-in-the-blank, matching, yes/no (or true/false), drag and drop into text, drag and drop onto image etc.
- Multiple-choice question (MCQ): A Multiple-Choice Question consists of a question (aka stem) and several alternative answers, among which are the correct ("keyed") answer (one usually or more) and one or more incorrect ("distractor") answers.

Example:

If $x=5$ and $y=2$, what is $x-y$?

- a. 7
- b. 3
- c. 5
- d. 10
- e. 8

Example:

What the acronym of SWOT analysis means?

- a. Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
- b. Strategy, Work, Office and Team spirit
- c. Strength, Willingness, Opportunity and Target
- d. Strategic goals, Working capital, Organizational Change and Test marketing.

→ Fill in the Blanks Question: The Fill in the Blanks allows e-learning designers to create cloze tests. Portions of words or sentences are removed from a text and the trainee is asked to provide the missing word or words.

Example:

(1) is known as the "red planet" because of its surface color.

Correct answer/s: 1. Mars
Matching Question: Matching questions have a content area and a list of names or statements that must be correctly matched against another list of names or statements. For example, "Match the Capital with the Country" with the two lists: "Canada, Italy, Japan" and "Ottawa, Rome, Tokyo".

→ Yes/no (or true/false) Question: In this kind of question only two choices for an answer are given: True or False. The question content can include an image or a code (html or other).

Example:

Every decision-making process produces a final choice, which may or may not prompt action.

True / False

Technical tips

The following paragraphs summarize the basic properties of an MCQ, but is applicable to all types of closed-ended questions.

Remember (a) to phrase the question (stem) in a clear and meaningful way and (b) to match the question (and correct answer) to learning outcomes and the wrong answers to common misconceptions associated with these learning outcomes (avoid obviously wrong or silly distractors). In the bullets below, you will find some instructions regarding the questions and the answers:

→ Question (stem)

Concise, clear text, without useless references. Avoid negative phrasing. Can contain an image.

→ Possible answers

- a) At least 4, numbered

- b) Each possible answer must be chosen carefully, so as not to overlap and to be clearly mutually exclusive
- c) Avoid "none of the above", "all of the above" or combinations (i.e. "1 and 3")
- d) The correct answer must correspond to one learning outcome and should be possible to deduct it from the learning material
- e) The wrong answers must correspond to common misconceptions
- f) The correct answer should not be (too) obvious

→ Correct answer

To keep it simple, only one answer should be unquestionably correct. Give its number here

→ Response to correct answer

Congratulating text with possible suggestions for follow up learning steps or further readings

→ Response to wrong answer(s)

- a) Could be the same for all wrong answers or different for each
- b) If the same feedback is chosen, then a generic statement explaining why the answer was wrong citing the most common misconceptions and which answer is correct should be given, followed by what the student should read in order to repair the misconceptions
- c) If different feedback should be given per wrong answer, then make sure that the feedback identifies the student misconception that led to the wrong answer and indicates what the student should read in order to repair the specific misconception

→ Number of times a question can be taken

This information indicates how many times the trainee can attempt to answer the question before feedback (other than correct / not correct) will be presented. Usually this number is 1.

→ Is the question part of a test?

If so, then the answers to all questions of the test are usually presented at the end of the test, together with the total score.

→ Workload estimation in TB3a – Field 7

For each assessment object the workload estimation is the accumulation / sum of each individual question's workload this object consists of.

- a) Time for responding to a quiz: for questions of types like "multiple choice" or "fill in the blanks" or "matching" is more or less 5 min (each)
- b) Questions of type "yes/no (or true/false)" is more or less 3 min (each).